

Implementation of Solar Powered Square Shaped Vertical Axis Mirror Reflection to Manage Peacock Movements in Agricultural Areas

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Abstract— The solar-powered square-shaped vertical axis mirror reflection system is implemented to manage peacock movements in agricultural areas. Peafowls, particularly peacocks, often cause significant damage to crops due to their erratic behavior and attraction to farming environments. The proposed system utilizes mirrors positioned with a vertical axis to reflect light, creating visual disturbances that deter peacocks from entering agricultural zones. Powered by solar energy, the system ensures a sustainable, cost effective and eco-friendly solution to manage wildlife without relying on chemicals or physical barriers. Solar power ensures continuous operation, even in remote areas, making it ideal for large agricultural spaces this innovative approach offers a practical and environmentally friendly solution for managing wildlife while promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

Keywords—solar panel, battery, DC gear motor, mirrors, horn speaker, IC 4440.

I. INTRODUCTION

Farming has always been a delicate balance between nature and human effort. Farmers put in months of hard work to grow their crops, only to find that wildlife, including peacocks, can cause unexpected damage. While peacocks are admired for their beauty and cultural significance, they can be a real challenge for farmers when they invade agricultural fields. These birds often target crops, pecking at grains, fruits and vegetables, leading to significant financial losses. The problem with peacocks is that they are highly adaptable and intelligent. Traditional deterrent methods such as scarecrows, loud noises or manual patrolling often lose effectiveness over time because the birds become accustomed to them. Additionally, hiring labor to monitor fields around the clock is expensive and impractical for many farmers. The challenge, therefore, is to create a system, effective and sustainable one that not require constant human intervention while ensuring peacocks stay away from crops. To address this challenge, we have developed a smart crop monitoring system for peacock deterrence. Unlike traditional scare tactics, this system is designed to operate continuously, creating an environment where peacocks feel uncomfortable and choose to stay away. The system utilizes a combination of sound based and visual deterrents, powered by a solar energy system to ensure uninterrupted operation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Abed et al had proposed a system that offered robust crop protection while aiding environmental conservation and preserving local wildlife in Rajasthan, India. This paper underscored the importance of adopting IoT based technologies for sustainable agriculture. It was a valuable resource for researchers, agronomists and various agriculture stakeholders to implement these advancements. This system held promise for enhancing crop security, minimizing resource waste and ensuring food chain stability for generations to come.

Akash Prajapati et al had developed a system for detecting birds in high definition video has been developed, addressing critical applications such as aviation safety, bird protection and ecological studies of migratory birds. The system leverages deep learning techniques, particularly convolutional neural networks, along with background visualization, contour detection and classification confusion matrices. Principal component analysis is employed to optimize deep features, effectively reducing data size, minimizing training and testing time, and improving recognition accuracy, especially when integrated with neural network classifiers.

Akanksha Mishra et al had developed a smart animal repelling device that seeks to safeguard crops from ungulate assaults, substantially reducing production expenditures. This is achieved by developing virtual fences that use Artificial Intelligence and ultrasonic emission. This study introduced a comprehensive distributed system for resource management in edge or fog settings. The framework leveraged the principle of containerization and utilizes docker containers to execute Internet of Things applications in microservices. The software system inside the suggested structure could include various IoT applications and resources.

Bejeras et al had developed a bird and human detection system for crop field breach surveillance using single shot multi box detector algorithm. Using the SSD algorithm, a cutting edge object detection method, the suggested system analyzed surveillance photos to identify and categorize humans and birds in crop fields. The system achieved a high accuracy of 89.78%, with an average precision of 73.85% for human detection and 88% for bird detection. The system provided real-time monitoring, enhancing farm security and minimizing crop losses. Its high detection accuracy

demonstrated the potential for AI driven surveillance in agricultural protection. The implementation of this technology enabled early intervention, reducing human wildlife conflicts and improving farm management efficiency.

Deotale et al had designed an automated perspicacious crop aegis system is proposed utilizing Internet of Things. The system consists of ESP8266, soil moisture sensor, dihydrogen monoxide sensor, GPRS and GSM module, servo motor, dihydrogen monoxide pump, etc. to obtain the required output. As soon as any kineticism is detected the system will engender an alarm to be taken and the lights will glow up implemented at every corner of the farm. The system enhanced farm security by providing real time alerts and automated responses to potential threats. Its IoT based design ensured efficient resource management while minimizing manual intervention.

Gajanan et al had proposed a device that can assist farmers in overcoming these challenges. The device utilized components such as arduino, a PIR motion sensor, a buzzer, LED lights, and a GSM module. It is self-assured to enhance crop yields, ultimately contributing to the economic well being of these farmers. The system generated animal specific frequency spectrum signals, effectively warning the targeted animals of potential danger and facilitating their safe retreat. The device was based on motion detecting sensors and was specifically designed for crop monitoring.

The literature survey highlights various studies on smart agricultural protection systems, IoT in mitigating crop damage. minimize false alarms and enhance farm security. Studies on IoT based monitoring systems showcase their effectiveness in real time surveillance, irrigation and precision agriculture, optimizing resource usage while reducing manual intervention. Investigations into motion detection and acoustic repellent systems highlight non-invasive methods for wildlife deterrence, ensuring both crop protection and ecological balance. Additionally, research on water management and irrigation underscores the importance of smart farming techniques in conserving water and maintaining soil health. Overall, these studies collectively suggest that IoT into agriculture enhances productivity, improves sustainability, and reduces economic losses while promoting efficient farm management.

III. DESCRIPTION OF EXISTING SYSTEM

farmers have struggled to protect their crops from various pests and wildlife, including peacocks. These birds, though often revered for their beauty and cultural significance, pose a significant threat to agricultural produce. Peacocks primarily feed on grains, fruits and vegetables, often causing extensive damage to farmland. To mitigate these losses, farmers have historically relied on various traditional methods to deter peacocks from entering their fields. While some of these methods have been effective in the short term, they often require constant human intervention and have limitations that reduce their long term sustainability. One of the most commonly employed methods to scare away peacocks involves creating loud noises. Farmers use metal plates, drums and other makeshift objects to produce sudden startling sounds whenever peacocks enter their fields. The sharp noises startle the birds, making them flee in fear. Some farmers even resort to shouting or clapping to achieve a similar effect. While this method is simple and cost effective,

it requires continuous human presence in the field, making it labour intensive. Additionally, peacocks may gradually become accustomed to the noise, reducing its effectiveness over time. The need for repeated manual intervention also makes it impractical for large farmlands. Another noise based deterrent involves using firecrackers or similar explosive sounds to scare away peacocks. The sudden, loud noise mimics the sound of a predator or a threatening situation, forcing the birds to flee. This method is commonly used during critical crop growing periods when the presence of peacocks is high. However, firecrackers pose a fire hazard, especially in dry agricultural regions. This method is not environmentally friendly and may disturb other wildlife. Some farmers install low voltage electric fences around their fields to create a boundary that prevents peacocks from entering. The mild electric shock discourages the birds from attempting to cross the fence. Although this method can be effective to some extent, it raises several concerns. It poses a potential risk to other animals and farm workers. The cost of setting up and maintaining an electric fence can be high for small scale farmers. Furthermore, peacocks, being strong fliers, can easily bypass the fence by flying over it.

Fig.1. Existing of deterrence to prevent peacock

the methods such as low voltage electric fencing, rope fencing and manual sound that are used in the existing system by the farmers. Farmers use rope fencing and net barriers to restrict peacock movement in farmlands. These barriers act as a physical deterrent, preventing the birds from entering specific areas. While net fencing can be somewhat effective for smaller areas, peacocks can easily fly over rope fences, making them largely ineffective. Net fencing requires regular maintenance, as wear and tear can create gaps that allow entry.

IV. CHALLENGES IN THE EXISTING SYSTEM

One of the major challenge is the inefficiency of traditional noise based deterrents. Farmers commonly use loud sounds such as banging metal plates, firecrackers or manually shouting to scare away peacocks. However, this method requires continuous human intervention, making it impractical for large scale farming. Additionally, peacocks often become habituated to repetitive sounds over time, reducing the effectiveness of this deterrent. Firecrackers, while momentarily effective, also pose safety risks, contribute to noise pollution and can disturb other wildlife in the area. Another significant issue is the limited effectiveness of physical barriers. Rope fencing and net enclosures are

frequently used to prevent peacocks from entering farmland. However, peacocks, being strong fliers, can easily bypass these barriers by flying over them. Low voltage electric fencing, though more effective in restricting movement, presents risks to farmworkers and other wildlife. Moreover, the cost of installing and maintaining electric fencing can be prohibitively high for small scale farmers, making it an unsustainable long term solution. Guard animals, such as trained dogs, are sometimes used to chase away peacocks, but this method has its drawbacks. Training dogs to effectively deter peacocks without harming them requires time and expertise. Additionally, farm dogs may become ineffective if they do not actively patrol the fields or if the peacocks learn to evade them. In some cases, dogs may chase peacocks away temporarily, but the birds often return once the threat is gone, leading to a recurring problem for farmers. The cost and maintenance requirements of existing deterrence methods also pose significant challenges. High tech solutions, such as motion activated sound deterrents or electric fencing, involve initial installation costs and ongoing maintenance expenses.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed smart crop monitoring system is sustainable and efficient solution designed to prevent peacock interference in agricultural fields. By integrating with key deterrent components such as a sound based deterrent system, a rotating mirror mechanism and a solar power system, the system ensures continuous operation without manual intervention. The sound based deterrent system plays pre-recorded predator calls, distress signals and human voices at random intervals, preventing peacocks from becoming accustomed to the sounds. Simultaneously, the rotating mirror mechanism reflects unpredictable flashes of sunlight, creating a visual deterrent that confuses and discourages peacocks from landing. This setup not only reduces operational costs but also makes the system eco-friendly and energy efficient. The deterrent mechanisms are always active, preventing peacocks from adapting to the environment.

A. BLOCK DIAGRAM:

Fig.3. Block Diagram of Proposed System

B. FLOW CHART:

Fig.4. Flow Chart of Proposed System

C. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION:

The smart crop monitoring system is designed as a fully automated, energy efficient solution to protect farmlands from peacock interference. The hardware implementation consists of key components, including a sound based deterrent system, a rotating mirror mechanism, a solar panel, a battery backup and supporting electronic circuits. These components work together to ensure continuous operation without requiring human intervention.

Hardware Components:

[i] Solar Panel: A solar panel is a device that converts sunlight into electrical energy using photovoltaic cells. These cells are made of semiconductor materials.

Fig.5.Solar Panel

[ii] Battery: A battery is a device that stores and converts chemical energy into electrical energy, providing power for a wide range of application.

Fig.6. Battery

[iii] DC Gear Motor: A DC gear motor is a type of DC motor that integrates a gear reduction system to enhance torque output while reducing speed.

Fig.7. DC Gear Motor

[iv] Mirrors: The mirrors are smooth reflection surface that form images by reflecting light. Most commonly mirrors are made from glass with a reflective coating such as silver or aluminium applied to the back.

Fig.8. Mirrors

[v] IC 4440: The audio IC 4440 is a popular dual channel audio amplifier IC known for its high power output, low distortion and thermal stability.

Fig.9. IC 4440

b. Specifications:

TABLE.1. Specifications of Thermal Image Camera

Solar Panel	12V,2A
Battery	12V,2.5A
DC Gear Motor	12V,1A
Mirrors	Angle(45°)

D. WORKING OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Peacocks are known to damage crops by feeding on seeds, shoots and mature plants, leading to significant yield loss. Traditional methods such as scarecrows, manual monitoring and chemical deterrents have limited effectiveness and require constant human intervention. To address this issue, a smart crop monitoring system is proposed, offering a sustainable solution for crop protection. This system is designed to operate continuously without the need for detection, ensuring continuous protection against peacock interference. It utilizes a sound based deterrent mechanism, which plays pre-recorded predator calls, distress signals and human voices to scare away peacocks effectively. Additionally, a reflection based deterrent is implemented using rotating mirrors mounted on a motorized disc, reflecting sunlight unpredictably to create a disorienting effect. The entire system is powered by solar energy, ensuring an eco-friendly and self-sustaining operation that eliminates the need for external power sources. A microcontroller acts as the central command unit, managing power distribution and activating deterrent mechanisms efficiently. By leveraging renewable energy and automated deterrent techniques, the proposed system provides a cost effective, low maintenance and long term solution for farmers struggling with peacock related crop damage.

E. OPERATION OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

The smart crop monitoring system is designed to provide continuous energy efficient protection for agricultural fields by deterring peacocks from damaging crops. Unlike conventional bird deterrent methods that require human intervention or motion detection based activation, this system operates continuously, ensuring that deterrent mechanisms remain active at all times. It uses a combination of sound based and reflection based deterrent techniques, powered by a solar panel with a battery backup, making it self-sustaining and cost effective for farmers. The system incorporates a speaker module that plays pre-recorded sounds at specific intervals. These sounds include predator calls such as those of eagles and hawks, distress signals of peacocks and human voices, which trigger a fear response in the birds, discouraging them from landing or staying in the field. To prevent peacocks from adapting to the sound patterns, the system randomizes playback

sequences to ensure unpredictability. Predator calls give the illusion that a threat is nearby, distress signals make peacocks believe that their species is in danger and human voices suggest human presence, all of which encourage peacocks to leave the area immediately. A motorized rotating disc with mounted mirrors is used to create random light reflections across the field. As sunlight hits the mirrors, the reflections move unpredictably, creating a disorienting effect for peacocks. Since birds are highly sensitive to sudden flashes of light, this method enhances the effectiveness of the sound deterrent system, making it harder for peacocks to become accustomed to the deterrent stimuli. This ensures that the reflection deterrent remains active throughout the day and night, preventing peacocks from finding opportunities to enter the field. Unlike motion activated bird deterrents, which may not always detect smaller movements or distant birds, this system operates continuously without requiring any detection mechanism. The constant activation of deterrents ensures that peacocks never feel safe enough to approach the crops.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig.10[i]. Implementing the developed model in the agriculture field

Fig.10[ii]. Reflections from the vertical axis mirror on implementing the model in the field

The proposed deterrent system was tested in a real agricultural field to evaluate its effectiveness in repelling peacocks. The results indicate a significant reduction in peacock intrusions, The rotating mirrors created unpredictable reflections that startled the birds, while the horn speaker distress calls and predator sounds reinforced their aversion. The synchronization between these deterrents further enhanced their impact, making it difficult for the birds to adapt to the system. Power efficiency was also analyzed, with the solar panel providing sufficient energy for continuous operation. The system maintained stable performance throughout the observation period, with no significant power fluctuations or failures. Farmers provided positive feedback, reporting a noticeable improvement in crop protection and a significant reduction in damage caused by peacocks. They appreciated the system operation, which minimized labour requirements and offered a practical, long term solution for large scale agricultural applications. Furthermore, observations showed that the peacocks did not develop resistance to the deterrent system, as the combination of reflections and varying sound patterns prevented habituation. The adaptability of the system in different environmental conditions and field layouts also demonstrated its versatility in real world agricultural scenarios. Farmers suggested minor adjustments in sound frequency and mirror placement to enhance deterrence further, highlighting the importance of continuous system optimization based on user feedback. The implementation of the system during the field experiment is clearly illustrated in the figure 8.1, showing the actual deployment and operational setup in the agricultural environment. From the discussion and field results, self-powered, effective and maintenance friendly, making it suitable for real world agricultural applications.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The first step the proposed smart crop monitoring system has proven to be an effective, reliable and eco-friendly solution for preventing peacock intrusion and safeguarding agricultural crops. By integrating mechanical components such as a DC gear motor driven rotating mirror assembly with electronic components like a horn speaker and IC 4440 amplifier, powered entirely by a solar and battery system, the model successfully operates autonomously without human intervention. The field implementation demonstrated that the combination of flashing mirror reflections and sound based deterrence significantly reduces the presence of peacocks in the protected area. The system is capable of making it suitable for long term deployment in remote or unattended agricultural fields. This Mini project-II not only addresses the specific problem of peacock induced crop damage but also serves as a sustainable and scalable solution for future wildlife management applications.

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